

“Economic Developments in Turkey According to British Annual Reports, 1980-1990”

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“İngiliz Yıllık Raporlarına Göre Türkiye’deki Ekonomik Gelişmeler, 1980-1990”

ABSTRACT

The Turkish economy transitioned from a state-led development model to a free-market structure between 1930 and 1990. Statism prevailed in the 1930s, while the economy contracted in the 1940s because of war. Liberal experiments failed in the 1950s; planned development and five-year plans came to the forefront in the 1960s, but foreign exchange shortages and low agricultural productivity persisted. The 1970s brought severe economic instability with political crises, oil shocks, and embargoes. After 1980, under Özal's leadership, a transformation was achieved through export-led growth, currency liberalization, and incentives for foreign investment. Exports and growth increased, but high inflation and public finance problems continued.

Keywords: Turkey, Economy, Liberalization, Statism, Planned Economy.

Öz

Türkiye ekonomisi 1930–1990 arasında devletçi kalkınma modelinden serbest piyasa yapısına geçti. 1930’larda statizm hâkimken, 1940’lar savaşın etkisiyle daraldı. 1950’lerde liberal denemeler başarısız oldu; 1960’larda planlı kalkınma ve beş yıllık planlar öne çıktı, ancak döviz darboğazı ve düşük tarım verimliliği sürdü. 1970’ler siyasi krizler, petrol şokları ve ambargolarla ağır ekonomik istikrarsızlık getirdi. 1980 sonrası Özal liderliğinde ihracata dayalı büyüme, döviz serbestisi ve yabancı sermaye teşvikleriyle dönüşüm sağlandı. İhracat ve büyüme arttı, ancak yüksek enflasyon ve kamu maliyesi sorunları devam etti.

Anahtar kelimeler: Türkiye, Ekonomi, Liberalleşme, Devletçilik, Planlı Ekonomi.

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Introduction

As in every country, the transition from a single-party system to a multi-party system in Türkiye was not an easy process. Despite their landslide victory in the 1950 general elections, the new Democratic Party leaders were rightly suspicious that many high-ranking bureaucrats and military officers would retain their historical allegiance to the People's Republican Party (PRP) while in opposition. Consequently, they increasingly intensified their measures to diminish the power and influence of their opponents.¹ For example, proposals to establish a committee to investigate allegations of subversive activities by the PRP were a major factor in the anti-Democratic coup of 1960. Before 1950, politics was confined to a small elite within the bureaucracy and an even smaller number of entrepreneurs and businesspeople, almost all of whom knew each other. However, after the first open elections in 1950, Turkish politicians were forced to find little other way than to respond to a broad national constituency and maximize the distribution of resources and the rewards of office on a much broader scale. The Democrats' rhetorical support for free enterprise is often overstated. However, the period during which they attempted to embrace liberal economic policies was relatively brief, and as early as 1954, they were reverting to more overtly statist measures, including strengthening bureaucratic control over a significant portion of economic activity.² The 1960 military coup was clearly aimed at overthrowing the increasingly authoritarian Democratic Party government. Since this appeared to be the sole objective of the military coup plotters, groups of influential intellectuals and officials took advantage of the situation to implement their own reform programs. One of these was an attempt to centralize previously disorganized economic interventions within a new state planning agency empowered to allocate cheap state credit and scarce foreign currency. Such measures led to both an increase in administrative power and an increase in the number of interest groups with more pressing demands. They also helped intensify the rapid process of economic and social change characterized by increased industrialization, urbanization, and labour migration abroad. The result was the creation of new classes, new relationships between interest groups and the government, and a new political and electoral geography at the national level.³ Despite the lack of structural economic reforms, the Turkish economy grew at the target rate set by the State Planning Organization (SPO) in the 1960s. This was practically an industrial revolution, a kind of upsurge few Third World countries had achieved. The global economic climate was favourable. More importantly, Turkish workers in Europe began sending large amounts of remittances home, enabling the country to import capital goods and raw materials for its industry and maintain a stable balance of payments. Unfortunately, long-term economic growth was unbalanced and unhealthy. Production in agriculture and industry increased only 75%, not as rapidly as planners had hoped, while growth in construction and services, moreover, made the economy heavily dependent on remittances sent by Turks working abroad, a source of unpredictability and dependent on the economic recovery in Europe. When the economic recession began in the early 1970s, the consequences for Turkey were severe. By the end of the 1960s, however, the character of the Turkish economy and society had changed almost beyond

¹ TNA/FO371 /95267/RK I O11/1, Turkey: Annual Review for 1950. Şevket Pamuk, *Türkiye'nin 200 Yıllık İktisadi Tarihi*, İş Bankası Yayınları, İstanbul 2018, passim.

² TNA/FCO9/RK101 I/I, Turkey: Annual Review for 1954. Korkut Boratav, *Türkiye İktisat Tarihi, 1908-2002*, İmge Yayınları, Ankara 2003, passim.

³ TNA/FO371/160212/RK1011/1, Turkey: Annual Review for 1960. Nazif Ekzen, *Türkiye Kısa İktisat Tarihi (1946'dan 2008'e)*, ODTÜ Yayıncılık, Ankara 2009, passim.

recognition. Before the 1960s, Turkey was predominantly an agricultural country, with a small state-dominated industrial sector. By the end of the decade, a significant private industrial sector had emerged, so much so that industry's contribution to GDP nearly equalled that of agriculture. However, the Turkish economy still had a long way to go before it could recover.⁴

The Justice Party, the successor to the dissolved Democrat Party, was the first to benefit from the 1960 coup. Despite the military's efforts to block it, it out represented its rival, the Republican Party (PRP), in every general election between 1961 and 1971. The Justice Party was initially forced to form short-lived coalitions with the PRP. However, after its decisive victory in the 1965 elections, it managed to form a single-party government under its new leader, Süleyman Demirel. Demirel consolidated the party's organizational power by exercising his control over a highly politicized planned economic program. But he also witnessed the gradual weakening of this power as right-wing elements under the same Demirel leadership distanced themselves from him and formed new organizations such as the Nationalist Movement Party and the Islamist National Order Party. One explanation for this was that frequently conflicting economic interests were increasingly unable to coexist within a single organization. Another was the increasing militancy of some worker and student organizations. Many soldiers shared this concern, and in 1971, they launched a second campaign to put an end to the escalating administrative chaos and political violence.⁵

1980

Realising their own limitations, the Generals have continued the economic policy introduced by Demirel, and employed its architect, Turgut Özal, to run it. It would, however, be premature to say that the economy has started to mend. Certain positive things have been achieved: inflation (still over 80 per cent) and the money supply have been brought under partial control; consumption has been sharply reduced; a start has been made towards reforming the state sector of the economy. The procedures for both exporters and foreign investors have been simplified, though obstacles remain. A three-year stand-by agreement has been negotiated with the International Monetary Fund (IMF), and further balance of payments support obtained through the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), in which the United States and the Federal Republic of Germany have the largest share. On the other hand, industrial production has been hardly, if at all, better than in 1979, through a combination of reduced internal demand, tight money, strikes, and shortages of energy and raw materials. Exports have not markedly increased in volume compared with 1979, although there were some more promising signs late in the year. The oil bill (over \$3 billion) representing at least 45 per cent of total imports, already exceeds the total of visible export earnings. The trade imbalance (\$3,5 billion in 1980) must be financed by invisible earnings, mainly workers' remittances (c. \$2 billion), and by loans. The latter increase the burden of debt (currently estimated at \$15 billion not including interest payments), and although the immediate strain has been relieved by the rescheduling of debts falling due in 1980-83, the future is being progressively mortgaged. Foreign investors and commercial banks have been chary of putting more money into Turkey; indeed, during the year the latter took net transfers out. Unemployment continues around the 20 per cent mark and is rising. Özal estimates that it will take Turkey 4-5 years to put her

⁴ TNA/FO371/160212/RK1011/1, Turkey: Annual Review for 1960. Boratav, Op. Cit., passim.

⁵ TNA/FO371/160212/RK1011/1, Turkey: Annual Review for 1960. Ekzen, Op. Cit., passim.

economy back into order, and this on the assumption that foreign help continues to be provided generously. Based on performance in 1980, 4-5 years looks optimistic.⁶

1981

Progress in the economy has been equally marked. The year was the second of the economic recovery programme, and the results were encouraging. Inflation was halved to an annual rate of about 35 per cent. Production slowly increased. Both these trends were helped by the suspension of collective bargaining and the ban on strikes and lockouts. The money supply has been kept under strict control. And, although this, combined with high interest rates, dented investment and placed some firms in difficulty the upward trend in exports noted in the last quarter of 1980 continued strongly throughout the year. At some \$4-5 billion, visible exports paid for more than 50 per cent of total imports. Workers' remittances reached some \$2, 5 billion, and receipts from Turkish contractors working abroad began to roll in. There was still a sizeable deficit on current account of over \$2 billion. But this was largely closed by the positive balance on capital account resulting from foreign aid receipts, principally from the OECD, IMF and the World Bank.⁷

Turkey's total debt burden now stands at over \$20 billion and presents a heavy call on her future resources. Even in 1981, and with the benefit of the various rescheduling agreements signed in 1980 and 1981, the payment of interest and some capital cost her about \$2 billion. The Turks managed this, although with some payment delays and under some pressure from their creditors. They were also able to reach an accommodation with most foreign banks concerned revising the 1979 rescheduling agreement covering commercial debt. They were, therefore, able to start the New Year with a relatively clean sheet and a somewhat improved credit rating.⁸

1982

One of the more significant events of the year was the dropping of the economic pilot, Turgut Özal. He had been the key figure in the economic recovery programme since its inception in January 1980 and had won the confidence of the International Monetary Fund, the World Bank, the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development, and Western bankers. His departure in July was sudden. True, he was not popular with everyone in either the public or private sectors since his free-market policies hurt some people in both. But they were manifestly working and seemed to have the backing of the Prime Minister and the Generals. His undoing came from the application of a free market to the financial sector. Competitive interest rates encouraged a rash of brokers whose main aim was to attract deposits by offering ludicrously high rates. The inevitable crash began when some depositors failed to get either their promised interest or their deposits back. Confidence failed. A few months later when the major broking house, Kastelli, collapsed, the finance minister was told to go. Özal refused to work with his nominated successor and went too. There was immediate speculation about a change of policy. The government, however, stated that there would be none and has stuck to it. The new Finance

⁶ FCO9/3317/WST014/2, Turkey: Annual Review for 1980. Ziya Öniş, "Turgut Özal and His Economic Legacy: Turkish Neo-Liberalism in Critical Perspective", *Middle Eastern Studies*, Vol. 40, No. 4, pp. 113-134. Oktay Yenal, *Cumhuriyet'in İktisat Tarihi*, Homer Kitabevi, İstanbul 2003, passim. Yenal, Op. Cit., passim. Ekzen, Op. Cit., passim. Pamuk, Op. Cit., pp. 223-263. Boratav, Op. Cit., passim.

⁷ FCO9/3668/WST014/3, Turkey: Annual Review for 1981. Öniş, Op. Cit., p. 113. Yenal, Op. Cit., passim. Ekzen, Op. Cit., passim. Pamuk, Op. Cit., pp. 223-263. Boratav, Op. Cit., passim.

⁸ FCO9/3668/WST014/3, Turkey: Annual Review for 1981. Öniş, Op. Cit., p. 113. Yenal, Op. Cit., passim. Ekzen, Op. Cit., passim. Pamuk, Op. Cit., pp. 223-263. Boratav, Op. Cit., passim.

Minister, Adnan Başar Kafaoglu, who was an adviser to General Evren, has promised a package of measures designed to improve performance, particularly in the tax and banking fields, but these have not yet appeared.⁹

What is of greater concern is that the drive behind the execution of the recovery programme diminished with Özal's departure? No-one has taken his place. His duties have been split between the new Minister of Finance and a new Minister of State for External Economic Relations, Sermet Pasin. Neither has the authority or the will that Özal had to get things done and cut through red tape. The power of the bureaucracy and the penchant for state control have begun to reassert themselves. Whether or not there is a causal connection, economic performance began to flatten in the second half of the year. Exports have been estimated at about \$5,6 billion (last year they were \$4,5 billion), although the target had earlier been raised to \$6,1 billion. Workers' remittances and tourism receipts will have fallen short of last year's figures. The broker debacle and the need to finance the purchase of agricultural products caused an unwelcome surge in the money supply in August/September. Nonetheless, the economic programme is still largely on target. The budget deficit, though larger than in 1981, has probably been financed by savings. The current account deficit is provisionally calculated at less than \$1,000 million and is covered by receipts on capital account, including foreign aid. The Turkish contracting industry now has a current overseas order book, largely in the Middle East, of at least \$13 billion. Inflation has been held down to between 25-30%, which recently permitted a slight lowering of deposit interest rates, and the economy has grown at an annual rate of about 4,5%. Both the IMF and OECD in their latest assessments give a favourable verdict on the progress towards economic recovery.¹⁰

1983

Turkey's progress to parliamentary government kept to schedule. Her economic performance was not so good. Throughout the year there was a sense of drift. The achievements of the previous two years were not followed up. In particular, the growth in exports began to tail away while the rate of inflation first stopped falling and then began to climb.¹¹

Continued export growth is vital if Turkey is to narrow her financing gap to a manageable size, attract renewed commercial lending and avoid a fresh debt rescheduling. Yet in the first ten months of 1985 exports grew by only 2,2%. External factors beyond Turkey's control were partly responsible, but apart from steady depreciation of the currency little was done to encourage exports. At the same time the earnings from workers' remittances, tourism and foreign investment either declined or made little progress. Imports increased by 4,9%, despite the fall in oil prices.¹²

The Minister of Finance continued until late into the summer to maintain that inflation would be kept to 20%. But by then it had become clear that this figure was hopelessly optimistic. Poor harvests, expensive company rescue operations, a depreciating lira and a desire to soften some

⁹ FCO9/4279/WST014/1, Turkey: Annual Review for 1982. Öniş, Op. Cit, p. 113. Yenal, Op. Cit., passim. Ekzen, Op. Cit., passim. Pamuk, Op. Cit., pp. 223-263. Boratav, Op. Cit., passim.

¹⁰ FCO9/4279/WST014/1, Turkey: Annual Review for 1982. Öniş, Op. Cit, p. 113. Yenal, Op. Cit., passim. Ekzen, Op. Cit., passim. Pamuk, Op. Cit., pp. 223-263. Boratav, Op. Cit., passim.

¹¹ FCO9/4833/WST014/1, Turkey: Annual Review for 1983. Öniş, Op. Cit, p. 114. Yenal, Op. Cit., passim. Ekzen, Op. Cit., passim. Pamuk, Op. Cit., pp. 223-263. Boratav, Op. Cit., passim.

¹² FCO9/4833/WST014/1, Turkey: Annual Review for 1983. Öniş, Op. Cit, p. 114. Yenal, Op. Cit., passim. Ekzen, Op. Cit., passim. Pamuk, Op. Cit., pp. 223-263. Boratav, Op. Cit., passim.

of the asperities of the recession in the pre-election period combined to fuel accelerating inflation. The final figure for 1983 is nearer 40% than 20%.¹³

Özal therefore inherits an awkward economic situation. He is acting swiftly to get a grip. Interest rates have been raised to encourage saving and investment and to reduce inflation. Tax incentives are being introduced to reward exporters and savers, and to facilitate the prompt and honest payment of taxes. The foreign exchange regulations and the highly protective import regime have been dramatically simplified and opened. A major reshuffle of ministerial responsibilities and departmental structure is designed to institute greater control and coordination over economic policy and its implementation. The effectiveness of these measures remains to be seen but already the drift has been replaced by a sense of purpose and activity.¹⁴

1984

The economic record is mixed. There are some clear successes. Overall GNP growth should reach 5,5% this year; industrial output is expanding by some 8,7% and agricultural by over 3%. Capacity utilisation is steadily rising. Exports are on target to grow by over 25% in dollar terms. Markets in the Middle East have been maintained and exports to the OECD countries are well up. The freeing of controls has not resulted in a flood of imports or a flight of capital. Foreign business interest (including British) is growing and Turkey's success in raising project finance and loans on the international market suggests increasing creditworthiness.¹⁵

But Turkey continues to run a balance of payments deficit, which she must bridge by further borrowing. From 1985 onwards her debt repayment obligations rise. The export drive may become harder to maintain. Her requirements for major capital expenditure will remain high and she has not yet attracted adequate inflows of foreign investment. Domestic inflation has yet to be controlled. The man in the street or the small businessman sees an inflation rate nearer 50% than 40%, a continuing squeeze on liquidity, bank loans at 70% and regular rises in the costs of basic commodities. He can look forward to VAT in the New Year at 10% and continuing unemployment at between 15% and 20% of the workforce.¹⁶

But progress in 1984 has been real and in assessing Turkey's prospects we should consider the intangibles as well as the statistics. The Government is economically responsible, and Özal understands the problems with which his country is faced. The five-year plan is not unrealistic. Moreover, it is indicative, not a fixed prescription. The course which it plots holds out much greater promise of putting Turkey on a path of sustainable growth than the autarkic policies of his predecessors.¹⁷

1985

¹³ FCO9/4833/WST014/1, Turkey: Annual Review for 1983. Öniş, Op. Cit, p. 114. Yenal, Op. Cit., passim. Ekzen, Op. Cit., passim. Pamuk, Op. Cit., pp. 223-263. Boratav, Op. Cit., passim.

¹⁴ FCO9/4833/WST014/1, Turkey: Annual Review for 1983. Öniş, Op. Cit, p. 114. Yenal, Op. Cit., passim. Ekzen, Op. Cit., passim. Pamuk, Op. Cit., pp. 223-263. Boratav, Op. Cit., passim.

¹⁵ FCO9/5184/WST014/1, Turkey: Annual Review for 1984. Öniş, Op. Cit, p. 115. Yenal, Op. Cit., passim. Ekzen, Op. Cit., passim. Pamuk, Op. Cit., pp. 223-263. Boratav, Op. Cit., passim.

¹⁶ FCO9/5184/WST014/1, Turkey: Annual Review for 1984. Öniş, Op. Cit, p. 115. Yenal, Op. Cit., passim. Ekzen, Op. Cit., passim. Pamuk, Op. Cit., pp. 223-263. Boratav, Op. Cit., passim.

¹⁷ FCO9/5184/WST014/1, Turkey: Annual Review for 1984. Öniş, Op. Cit, p. 115. Yenal, Op. Cit., passim. Ekzen, Op. Cit., passim. Pamuk, Op. Cit., pp. 223-263. Boratav, Op. Cit., passim.

If Turkey's leaders can feel some satisfaction at the country's political progress, the economy remains the key to the future. On the plus side a 5% growth rate has been maintained, and the balance of payments is much healthier. Exports have grown by about 13%, imports by rather less, and invisible earnings are sharply up. The overall deficit on the external account is likely to be about 30,9 billion in 1984. Turkey has met all her debt obligations in 1985 and is confident of doing so next year. The Central Bank also recognise the need to prevent an increase in short-term foreign debt and to manage its longer-term repayments to avoid peak years.¹⁸

But if Turkey is to sustain the 5% plus growth rate which a growing population requires and to meet her debt servicing obligations, continued expansion of her exports is vital. So far Turkish industry, with textiles in the vanguard, has responded well, mainly by taking up the slack in its under-utilised capacity. In future more investment will be required.¹⁹

Foreign investment is coming in only slowly. Internally financed investment is discouraged by high interest rates reflecting an inflation rate of 45% by the end of the year. This is down from 55% a year ago but well above the Government's target. The trend is likely to continue downwards with a target of 25% for 1986. But to achieve even 30%, the Government will have to reduce further the budget deficit and check monetary growth. The signs are that Özal intends to grasp these nettles more firmly in the New Year. There are other encouraging features. Value added tax (VAT) has substantially expanded the tax base; new measures to improve tax collection are in the pipeline and there are a healthy realism and openness about Turkish economic policy making. But the argument always comes back to inflation. Those on fixed incomes and low salaries (the mass of government employees) are feeling the pinch. Discontent has not reached the point where it threatens to produce decisive political opposition. But Özal knows that before 1988 he must show that he has the answer to inflation.²⁰

1986

The high hopes for 1986 engendered by the encouraging performance in 1985 and the prospects for considerable savings through lower oil prices proved excessive. The Current Account balance, the key to the maintenance of increasing international confidence in Turkish creditworthiness, was in deficit for the year by about \$1,3 billion, almost \$1 billion above forecast. Poor marketing of tourism adversely affected receipts. Meanwhile a surge of imported investment goods, mainly for the municipalities, and the collapse of Turkey's important export markets in Iran and Iraq affected the balance of trade. For the first time the Özal Government was unable to boast export growth. Latterly it has allowed a rapid slide in the exchange rate and introduced measures, including tax rebates and credits, to encourage exporters. But it will take time to replace the lost markets of the Middle East.²¹

Despite these setbacks Turkey continues to manage her debt servicing without recourse to the IMF. Her standing in international markets has improved, but to overcome the international

¹⁸ FCO9/5506/WST014/1, Turkey: Annual Review for 1985. Öniş, Op. Cit, p. 116. Yenal, Op. Cit., passim. Ekzen, Op. Cit., passim. Pamuk, Op. Cit., pp. 223-263. Boratav, Op. Cit., passim.

¹⁹ FCO9/5506/WST014/1, Turkey: Annual Review for 1985. Öniş, Op. Cit, p. 116. Yenal, Op. Cit., passim. Ekzen, Op. Cit., passim. Pamuk, Op. Cit., pp. 223-263. Boratav, Op. Cit., passim.

²⁰ FCO9/5506/WST014/1, Turkey: Annual Review for 1985. Öniş, Op. Cit, p. 116. Yenal, Op. Cit., passim. Ekzen, Op. Cit., passim. Pamuk, Op. Cit., pp. 223-263. Boratav, Op. Cit., passim.

²¹ FCO9/5813/WST014/1: Turkey: Annual Review for 1986. Öniş, Op. Cit, p. 117. Yenal, Op. Cit., passim. Ekzen, Op. Cit., passim. Pamuk, Op. Cit., pp. 223-263. Boratav, Op. Cit., passim.

debt hump ahead she needs to eschew short term borrowing, a shift which international banks may not yet be ready to underwrite.²²

Within Turkey the strengthening internal demand led to real growth of GNP of almost 8%, well above the planned 5%. Belatedly the Government introduced measures to curb imports and public investment, whilst re-emphasising its determination to continue to open the economy. In 1987 it aims to hold growth to 5% making inflation, more likely to be a significant factor at the next election, its prime target. The end of year inflation rate (wholesale prices) of 24.6% was a little below the Government's target of 25%. The statistical basis for the figure is questioned, but the trend is undoubtedly downwards from last year's 38%, though due more to lower oil prices and the weak dollar than tighter monetary or fiscal policies. A further reduction will be required before the cost of credit is low enough to encourage the private investment needed to sustain the growth of the industrial sector and its export performance. The target for 1987, though sensibly modest at 20%, may not be enough for this.²³

1987

The Government's inflation target for 1987 was 20%. The likely outturn is 50%. Retail prices will be up more. After 8% GNP growth in 1986, it will be nearly 7% in 1987 despite another 5% target. Letting the economy rip ahead of elections, Özal argued that, with high unemployment, rapid population growth and European aspirations, Turkey needed to grow fast; inflation was secondary; he could beat the balance of payments constraint. On that at least he has so far done well. Exports are up 33%, tourist receipts and remittances are buoyant. The current account will be no more than a third the 1986 level. But external debt is \$34 billion, and the writing is on the wall. Özal, the erstwhile IMF disciple, can surely read it. The avalanche of price rises which stunned the ordinary Turkish voter only two days after the elections seemed to confirm this. So does the new Government's commitment to cut inflation and reinforce the economic reforms introduced since 1983. But the real test will be their ability to cut back on public sector spending.²⁴

1988

A year ago, the British Ambassador had written that the real test would be the authorities' ability to cut back on public spending in 1988. They had clearly failed it. The public sector deficit, at some 7% of GNP, was down only a single point on the previous year. The rise inflation from 50% to 75% was largely attributable to that failure. An intermittently tight monetary response was not adequately supported by effective fiscal measures; overspending was allied to failure to collect taxes efficiently. Nonetheless, and despite much chopping and changing of official policy, there was a substantial slowing of the rate of economic growth from about the middle of the year. The widely held expectation that the 5% growth target of GNP would be overshoot as

²² FCO9/5813/WST014/1: Turkey: Annual Review for 1986. Öniş, Op. Cit, p. 117. Yenal, Op. Cit., passim. Ekzen, Op. Cit., passim. Pamuk, Op. Cit., pp. 223-263. Boratav, Op. Cit., passim.

²³ FCO9/5813/WST014/1: Turkey: Annual Review for 1986. Öniş, Op. Cit, p. 117. Yenal, Op. Cit., passim. Ekzen, Op. Cit., passim. Pamuk, Op. Cit., pp. 223-263. Boratav, Op. Cit., passim.

²⁴ FCO9/6180/WST014/1, Turkey: Annual Review for 1987. Öniş, Op. Cit, p. 118. Yenal, Op. Cit., passim. Ekzen, Op. Cit., passim. Pamuk, Op. Cit., pp. 223-263. Boratav, Op. Cit., passim.

usual may prove to have been wrong. Indeed, the year ended with bank lending rates around 140% and businessmen complaining of a risk of stagflation.²⁵

Whatever business fears, there is a potentially crucial difference between this situation and previous economic crises. There is no balance of payments problem; and that despite external debt totalling nearly \$40 billion. The balance of payments was near equilibrium. Exports continued to do well; imports grew less fat than forecast. Tourist revenues may have exceeded \$2,5 billion. The 1988 performance on external account was excellent.²⁶

1989

Although Foreign attention remained principally concentrated on Turkey's admirable performance on external account, 1989 was a second excellent year in a row. The surplus was likely to have been over \$700 million; foreign direct investment approached \$650 million; external debt was down to about \$35 billion. The domestic view was not so rosy. Public fixed capital investment was down but the PSBR was still some 6% of GNP. Inflation was down a bit at 69%, with GNP growth only 1 to 2%. Business complained of stagflation. Unemployment increased; at a rough guess it was around 17%. Currency revaluation put exporters under pressure; tourist revenue and remittances were up but exports duly stagnated.²⁷

1990

Economic performance in 1990 was every bit as volatile as Turkey's politics: Growth 9%; Imports up 45% (Exports up 7%); a Current Account deficit of over \$2 billion after surpluses in 1988 and 1989; net Foreign Capital Investment up 36%; a strong Reserves position following the gamble taken over TL Convertibility, and the currency's further substantial real appreciation; Inflation down from 68% at end 1989 to 'only' 49% at end 1990, although again rising under the pressures of oil prices, labour troubles and a budget deficit up by 63%. Economic performance is, and is likely to remain, uneven and unpredictable. The high inflation, which is one of the main causes of political instability, will continue. The Current Account is vulnerable. Yet of the resilience of the economy there can be no doubt. The ride may have been bumpy and the driving reckless but 6% pa average growth since 1985 whilst meeting external obligations promptly is no mean record.²⁸

Conclusion

Over the ten-year period from 1980 to 1990, Turkey underwent a significant transformation in its economic structure, shifting from a state-led, planned economy to a more liberal, export-oriented model.

The 1980s saw a major shift under Turgut Özal's leadership, with liberalization policies aimed at integrating Turkey into the global economy. Export-led growth, deregulation, and foreign investment were prioritized. While these reforms brought about higher growth rates

²⁵ FCO9/6642/WST014/2, Turkey: Annual Review for 1988. Öniş, Op. Cit, p. 119. Yenal, Op. Cit., passim. Ekzen, Op. Cit., passim. Pamuk, Op. Cit., pp. 223-263. Boratav, Op. Cit., passim.

²⁶ FCO9/6642/WST014/2, Turkey: Annual Review for 1988. Öniş, Op. Cit, p. 119. Yenal, Op. Cit., passim. Ekzen, Op. Cit., passim. Pamuk, Op. Cit., pp. 223-263. Boratav, Op. Cit., passim.

²⁷ FCO9/6988/WST014/2, Turkey: Annual Review for 1989. Öniş, Op. Cit, p. 120. Yenal, Op. Cit., passim. Ekzen, Op. Cit., passim. Pamuk, Op. Cit., pp. 223-263. Boratav, Op. Cit., passim.

²⁸ FCO9/1508/WST014/2, Turkey: Annual Review for 1990. Öniş, Op. Cit, p. 121. Yenal, Op. Cit., passim. Ekzen, Op. Cit., passim. Pamuk, Op. Cit., pp. 223-263. Boratav, Op. Cit., passim.

and improved external balances, inflation remained a chronic issue, and structural problems in public finance and state enterprises persisted.

By 1990, Turkey had achieved notable economic resilience, maintaining an average growth rate of 6% since 1985 and meeting its external obligations. However, high inflation, fiscal imbalances, and vulnerability to external shocks continued to pose challenges. The period concluded with a mixed legacy: substantial progress in liberalization and growth, yet unresolved macroeconomic instabilities that would shape the economic agenda of the following decade.

The period between 1980 and 1990 in the Turkish economy was marked by structural transformations and crises. At the end of the 1970s, Turkey was in a severe economic crisis. Foreign exchange shortages, high inflation, external debt problems, and import restrictions were straining the economy. With the January 24, 1980, Decisions, Turkey shifted from an import-substitution industrialization model to an export-oriented growth model. This marked the beginning of economic liberalization. The goal was to open the economy to the outside world and strengthen the free market mechanism. To achieve this, the exchange rate was liberalized, export incentives were increased, public spending was reduced, and interest rates were deregulated. As a result, exports increased, but in the short term, inflation rose and income distribution deteriorated.

During the 1980s, the structure of the economy shifted from agriculture and textile-based exports to industrial products. Inflation remained in double digits throughout the decade, and at times even reached triple digits. Between 1980 and 1988, an average growth rate of 4–5% was achieved, although it was volatile. The economy was supported by IMF and World Bank loans, but external debt stock increased. In 1989, capital movements were liberalized, which led to an influx of short-term hot money.

As a result, liberal policies increased income inequality. High inflation and interest rates made the investment environment challenging. Although exports grew, imports rose even faster, widening the current account deficit. After 1989, financial liberalization became uncontrolled, laying the groundwork for the 1994 crisis. Structural transformation increased unemployment. After the 1980 coup, trade union activities were restricted. Imported goods and consumer culture became widespread.

In summary, the 1980–1990 period was when Turkey opened its economy to the world and adopted an export-oriented growth model, but high inflation, income inequality, and external debt problems persisted. This process laid the foundation for the crises of the 1990s.

The January 24, 1980, Stabilization Program and subsequent reforms are presented in British reports as a “market reform” case in which Turkey shifted to an export-oriented growth strategy, accelerating steps toward exchange rate and interest rate liberalization as well as trade and financial liberalization. Following the oil shocks of the 1970s, the reforms are emphasized as being implemented under the supervision of the IMF and the World Bank, with adjustments in exchange rates and export promotion.

By the end of the decade, the liberalization of capital movements in 1989 is noted in British documents as a turning point that integrated Turkey into global financial flows. The reports focus on the opportunities and vulnerabilities associated with short-term capital inflows.

Recurring themes in these reports include:

1. **Intertwining of geopolitics and economics:** Economic issues are almost always discussed alongside the security of the Straits, Middle Eastern balance, and alliance politics; this linkage is evident from the statism of the 1930s to the “active neutrality” economy of the 1940s and the IMF-related notes of the 1950s.
2. **Balance of payments and foreign exchange shortages:** From the clearing arrangements of the 1930s, wartime scarcity economy, and the 1958 and 1970/77 episodes, to post-1980 mechanisms of exchange rate flexibility and export-oriented compensation. The language of the documents often revolves around exchange rates, reserves, external debt, and gold/sterling/dollar.
3. **Sterling and the Bretton Woods framework:** The 1947 convertibility crisis, Sterling Area arrangements, and foreign exchange allocation policies for the Middle East and Turkey are recorded as reflections of Britain’s own macroeconomic constraints on Ankara.
4. **The “stabilization program” narrative:** The 1958, 1970, and 1980 junctures are coded in the documents as levers of “stabilization–exchange rate adjustment–IMF-supported rebalancing.” For the 1980s, additional emphasis is placed on privatization, trade liberalization, and financial openness.

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